

Biochar is a potential use of agricultural residues and processing side-streams in Maharashtra, India

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Abstract

This study explores the potential of biochar as a sustainable solution for managing agricultural residues and food processing side-streams in Maharashtra, India. Following PRISMA 2020 literature review framework, the research assessed characteristics of feedstocks available in Maharashtra including sugarcane residues, rice husk and straw, cotton residues, tomato and grape pomace, and brewers' spent grains, for biochar production. The study also analysed the properties of derived biochars. Findings indicate that the biochar's properties important in its use in agriculture such as cation exchange capacity (CEC), pH, specific surface area (SSA), nutrient content are dependent on the original feedstock properties and conditions of pyrolysis. Biochar's benefits are well documented in some specific kinds of soil present in Maharashtra, while its effect on some other kinds of soils require more detailed scientific investigation. Risks related to presence of heavy metals, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), environmentally persistent free radicals (EPFRs) highlight importance of feedstock selection, optimized pyrolysis selection and biochar certification for its safety. Further research focused on barriers for pyrolysis implementation, techno-economic analysis and life cycle assessment (LCA) is advised. Overall, biochar production represents a promising pathway for greenhouse gases emissions reduction and soil health improvement in Maharashtra, provided that implementation strategies are tailored to local agroecological conditions and supported by enabling policies.

Key words: biochar, pyrolysis, India, Maharashtra, SAGE, feedstock, soil health, carbon sequestration, sustainable agriculture

1.Introduction

Agriculture in Maharashtra

Maharashtra is a state located in central India, occupying 307,690 square km² in Deccan plateau and Western Ghats (Encyclopaedia Britannica). Maharashtra, after north Indian states located in the Ganga Plain, is one of the most important agricultural regions of India (Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation, 2023). Maharashtra in 2020-21 was the biggest producer of soyabean. In 2023 it was the 4th biggest producer of fruits and vegetables (Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation, 2023). Other important crops include wheat, jowar (sorghum), cotton, pulses, rice, sugarcane and maize (Directorate of Economics and Statistics, 2022). Agriculture contributes around 11% to the state's GDP and employs over 50% of the workforce. (Directorate of Economics and Statistics, 2022). Land fragmentation is one of the factors limiting agricultural productivity, as many smallholders cannot implement mechanization on their farm (Solunke, 2020). The average size of a farm is 1.34 ha. 80% of the farms are smaller than 2 ha. Farms smaller than 2 ha occupy around 45% of arable land in the state (Maharashtra Institution for Transformation, 2025). Most of the arable lands are rain-fed (Solunke, 2020), therefore more vulnerable for climate-warming that leads to changes in rain patterns (Katalakute et al., 2016).

Residues produced from agricultural sources in Maharashtra exceed 152.25 MT yearly (Gabhane et al., 2016). There are a couple of traditional agrowaste utilisation techniques such as cattle feeding or composting, however a substantial amount of biomass remains unused on the farm, and the lack of developed markets prevents its further utilization. Some part of this biomass is burned on fields which leads to emission of greenhouse gases and significant air pollution, or dumped, which can result in contamination of surface and ground water and eventually also lead to greenhouse gas emissions (Gabhane et al., 2016).

Biochar technology

Biochar is a product of pyrolysis of biomass in high temperatures (above 250°C) without access to oxygen. Biochar production and storage in agricultural soils has a promising potential for sequestration of atmospheric carbon as the carbon in the product of pyrolysis has high chemical stability (Lehmann et al. 2015; Woolf et al., 2021; Sanei et al., 2025). Currently recognized guidelines proposed by Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (2019)

estimate that, depending on temperature of pyrolysis 65% to 89% of the total carbon stored in the soil in the form of biochar remains in the soil for at least 100 years. Apart from biochar, the products of the biomass pyrolysis consist of fuels in form of hydrogen and hydrocarbons both in liquid and gaseous form, which can be used as a source of climate-neutral energy (Lehmann & Joseph, 2024).

Storage of biochar in the soil has the potential of enhancing soil properties, resulting in a higher yield. Biochar can increase soil cation exchange capacity (CEC) (Liang et al., 200), which can help in more efficient soil fertilization by reducing run-offs (Lehmann & Joseph, 2024). Depending on feedstock used and temperature of pyrolysis, biochar's pH can vary. However as a rule it has an alkaline pH, which allows for its use for soil liming. For this reason biochar can have a particularly beneficial effect on acidic soils (Lehmann & Joseph, 2024). Biochar has also a potential for improving water retention in the soil. Due to its high porosity it is able to increase water storage potential in the soil, which benefits water stressed agricultural systems (Edeh et al., 2020). Apart from its capacity to change physical properties of the soil, biochar can be considered as a fertilizer as well. Biochar production leads to concentration of nutrients in the dry mass of the product, therefore biochar has higher mineral composition than the original biomass. It has particular significance in the case of Phosphorus (P) and Potassium (K), which remain in the final pyrolysis product even up to 100 percent (Liu et al., 2019). In the case of P, however, the bioavailability in biochar is lower than in the original biomass (Laghari et al., 2021). This effect is stronger with increasing temperature of pyrolysis (Glaser & Lehr, 2019). In the case of Nitrogen (N), a significant amount of this element transitions to the gas and liquid fractions during pyrolysis. Under low temperature pyrolysis conditions, up to 65% of N can remain in the biochar, which decreases as the pyrolysis temperature increases (Liu et al., 2019).

All things considered, pyrolysis is a technology, which can be a solution for biowaste management. Biochar has the potential to improve soil properties, reducing the use of resources, therefore it can be used for sustainable agriculture. Furthermore, biofuels, which are another product of pyrolysis, can be used as a climate neutral energy source. These can be used in the place of production or sold for revenue generation. On top of that, carbon sequestration in the agricultural soils in the form of biochar can make the entire process carbon negative, thereby contributing to climate change mitigation and, by carbon credits sale, generate additional income (Carbonfuture, 2025).

Research objectives

This study aims to summarize existing knowledge based on available literature on:

1. Agricultural residue generation in Maharashtra and existing residue management practices.
2. Properties of the feedstocks, identified as relevant in Maharashtra by SAGE feedstock consortium meeting (4th-5th of July, 2025, Bengaluru). Tomato agri-residues and processing side streams, rice husk and straw, wheat straw, cotton agricultural residues, grapes pomace, sugar cane residues, and brewers spent grains, will be analysed for the potential for usage as a substrate in pyrolysis process.
3. Properties of biochars from those feedstocks. The study will analyse potential environmental and agrarian benefits and risks for soil health in the environmental context of Maharashtra in context of properties of biochar derived from the specific feedstocks.

Due to time constraints, the research will not focus on a full techno-economic analysis and LCA of the potential implementation of biomass pyrolysis. However, it aims to present data in this area as well, which may serve as a direction for further studies within the consortium's work.

2.Methods

Methodology consisted of semi-systematic literature review. The workflow followed PRISMA 2020 guidelines (Page et al., 2021). The articles used for the report were retrieved via Google Scholar during the period from July to September 2025. Key words used for investigation of agriculture residue in were “agricultural waste” or “agricultural residues” and “tomato”, “rice husk”, “rice straw”, “wheat straw”, “cotton”, “grapes pomace”, “brewers spent grains” and “sugar cane” as well as “Maharashtra” or “India”. For the second and the third research objective, relevant feedstock were searched together with the phrase “biochar”. Later the phrase “biochar” was searched with the phrases “lateritic soil”, “black cotton soil”, “vertisol”, and “coastal saline soil”. Finally, the phrase “biochar” was searched together with phrases “LCA”, “life cycle assessment” and “techno-economic analysis”. Some studies were

selected by so-called “snowball effect”- identification of relevant literature through examination of the reference lists of already found articles. Study selection was conducted by a single reviewer. Screening was based on title and abstract relevance. For the first research objective only articles relevant from Maharashtra or India were selected. For the second and third research objective we selected the literature focusing on properties of listed above feedstock and its biochar derived from above, the influence on soil health (with special focus on kinds soils present in Maharashtra), carbon sequestration, crop yield, and economy. We focused only on effects on traditional soil agriculture, excluding research on soilless substrate, as it is not relevant for Maharashtra’s local agricultural landscape for now. The time range of publications searched was 2010-2025. Only articles in English were included. Due to time constraints, analysis of all the found articles was not feasible. For this reason the articles which were the most relevant to the context of local agricultural reality were chosen. Finally 53 reports were included in the review.

Results of the studies regarding available biomass for the pyrolysis purposes were summarised in a spreadsheet, presenting, when possible carbon content, results of proximate and elemental analysis, water content, and content of cellulose, hemi-cellulose, and lignin. Results on the biochar properties were summarized in another spreadsheet. These included temperature of pyrolysis, yield, carbon content, H/C ratio, O/C ratio, main nutrient content pH, CEC (cation exchange capacity), SSA (specific surface area), EC (electrical conductivity), and WHC (water holding capacity). Results of research on beneficial agronomic effects and environmental risks was provided in “results and discussion” section, preceded by summarized effects of the literature review about feedstock and biochar properties. Spreadsheets summarizing feedstock and derived biochar properties are available in supplementary material (S1).

3. Results and discussion

Agricultural residues and food processing side-streams in Maharashtra

Yearly generation of agricultural residues in Maharashtra was estimated by Gabhane et al. (2016) basing on agricultural production data from Economic Survey of Maharashtra 2013-2014 and RPR (residue to-product ratio), which is a specific value for every crop, and was taken as an average of the previous literature. Gabhane et al. (2016) identified sugarcane

cultivation as the biggest agro-waste generator in the state, followed by banana, soy bean, oilseed and sorghum.

The same study examined the utilization of the agro-residues on the farm level. Authors of the articles identified on-farm burning as a utilization of the agro-residues, however it should be considered more of a waste-management practice rather than as utilization (Jain et al., 2014). For this reason the data were recalculated and agro-residues generated from each crop were presented as a sum of agro-residues generated from the article and on-site burning. The numbers show that the utilization of the feedstock varies from 80% in case of sorghum to only 3 % in case of a sugar cane (Table 1). Notably, the crops with the highest total agro-waste production have the lowest utilization rate, what leads to significantly the highest net agro-waste generation by sugar cane (33.24 MT/y), banana (14.03 MT/y), and cotton (13.94 MT/y). Jain et al. (2014), estimate that that crop burning in Maharashtra led to emission of 10 335 700 t of CO₂ alone, accompanied by CO, NO_x, SO_x, non-methane volatile organic compounds, NH₃, HCN, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, and particle matter pollutants.

Table 1. Total net agro-waste generation in Maharashtra, as per RPR method. Source: Gabhane et al. (2016)

Crop	Total agro-waste generation [Mt/y]	Cattle feeding [%]	Composting or leaving for decomposition [%]	Burning [%]	Total utilization (excluding burning) [%]	Not utilized agro-waste [%]	Net agro-waste generation [Mt/y]
Sugar cane	34.27	0	3	8	3	97	33.24
Banana	16.50	2	13	8	15	85	14.03
Cotton	15.84	0	12	70	12	88	13.94
Soy bean	10.57	15	8	20	23	77	8.14
Oilseed	10.44	30	6	15	36	64	6.68
Sorghum	5.90	70	10	10	80	20	1.18
Maize	4.87	60	3	3	63	37	1.80
Rice	4.30	60	9	4	69	31	1.33
Wheat	2.93	70	6	2	76	24	0.70

Food processing residues are lower in total volume than agricultural residues, however they are available in large quantities in sites of food processing, therefore the cost of transport does not occur and their management is easier to coordinate. Grape pomace is the pulp, skin and seeds remaining after extraction of juice or wine, what constitute up to 40 % of a grape mass (Vasanthi, 2019). Although grape pomace have numerous compounds valuable for eg. in the

pharmaceutical industry, in the context of India, large quantities of grape pomace are wasted (Vasanthi, 2019). Brewers spent grains are a by-product of the brewing industry. They contribute to around 85% of waste generated by the brewing industry (Viridi et al., 2025). Similarly to grape pomace, regardless of its wide possible uses (e.g. food industry, livestock feed, biogas feedstock, cellulose production), brewers grain are frequently regarded as a waste (Viridi et al., 2025).

Feedstock categorization for biochar production

Feedstock used is one of the most influential factors affecting biochar properties, therefore its agronomic value (Lehmann & Joseph, 2024). The composition of the biomass affects properties of biochar such as the yield, pH, CEC, and nutrient content (Lehmann & Joseph, 2024). What is more, physical properties of feedstock such as water content, and bulk density affect the cost of collection and transportation of the biomass, therefore the analysis of biomass properties makes it possible to select a suitable material for pyrolysis. The summary of the properties of biochars derived from tomato residues, rice husk and straw, sugarcane leave and bagasse, cotton residues, grape pomace, and brewers spent grains was summarized and presented in the supplemental material (S1).

Proximate analysis provides information about moisture content, volatile matter, fixed carbon, and ash content of the biomass. The results of proximate analysis are summarized in tables 2 and 3. Moisture content was measured in several researches included in the analysis (Borel et al., 2020; Bushra and Remya, 2020; Castro et al., 2025; Da Silva Araújo et al., 2025 ; Elkhalfifa et al., 2022; Ferreira et al., 2021; Gupta et al., 2016; Phuong et al., 2015; Ishii and Furuichi, 2014; Jahirul et al., 2012; Kumar et al., 2022; Manríquez-Altamirano et al., 2021; Pirozzi et al., 2022; Primaz et al., 2021; Stylianou et al., 2013). The moisture content vary from 2.24% as the lowest values for brewers spent grains to 89% in case of tomato stems. It is however important to note, that the moisture content of the biomass used in laboratory experiments do not always correspond to moisture content of the biomass available in the market, as in some cases it was eg. sun-dried before analysis.

Table 2. Moisture content in different kinds of biomass

<i>Feedstock</i>	<i>Moisture content [%]</i>
Brewers spent grains	2.24 – 6.68
Sugarcane leaf	5.44 – 5.61
Sugarcane straw	4.01 - 8.52
Sugarcane bagasse	7.32 - 7.41

Cotton seed	8.43
Rice husk	9 – 14
Rice straw	6 – 25
Grape pomace	7.1 - 9.70
Tomato pomace	80.70 – 94
Tomato stems	89

Table 3. Volatile matter content, fixed carbon content and ash content in different kinds of biomass

<i>Feedstock</i>	<i>Volatile matter content [%]</i>	<i>Fixed carbon content [%]</i>	<i>Ash content [%]</i>
Brewers spent grains	73.18 – 83.30	9.51 – 19.30	3.22
Sugarcane leaf	72.33	10.67	6.38
Sugarcane straw	73.41 – 86.64	9.51	3.85
Sugarcane bagasse	76.93 – 80.98	7.52 – 11.33	4.09 – 4.41
Cotton seed	92.43	2.51	5.06
Rice husk	70.2 – 78.5	3.4 – 19.8	3.4 – 17
Rice straw	79	10.7	4.3
Grape pomace	69.3.	26.7	6.79
Tomato pomace	80.43.	28.21	3.47 – 23
Tomato stems	<i>n.d.</i>	<i>n.d.</i>	8 – 19

High water content in the biomass, despite affecting transportation cost, negatively affects biochar and liquid bio-fuel yield, as well as biochar's carbon stability (Jahirul et al., 2012). High moisture also negatively affects the biofuels quality, as the bio-oil may be produced with high moisture content which eventually reduces its calorific value. In general, a proper pyrolysis process needs moisture content below 5 wt%–15 wt% (Jahirul et al., 2012). Drying the biomass of a high moisture content may require more energy than the biomass store (Lehmann & Joseph, 2024), leading to negative energy balance. In cases when energy for drying is sourced from a fossil-dominated grid, it results in substantial greenhouse gases emission, which contradicts the rationale of operating such a system (Cowie et al., 2024).

Volatile matter refers to a non-aromatic, easily decomposable fraction of organic carbon in biomass, while fixed carbon refers to aromatic carbon that is thermally resistant (Hockaday et al., 2024). High values of volatile matter within feedstock favour creation of biofuels and syngas during pyrolysis, while high values of fixed carbon favour creation of biochar (Jahirul et al., 2012). Ash content refers to inorganic material remaining after oxidation of biomass (Lehmann & Joseph, 2024). Pyrolysis of biomass of the high ash content results in the high yield of biochar, which also has high ash content, therefore relatively low carbon content (Brown et al., 2024).

The major components of biomass are cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin, each of which is different in their decomposition behaviour (Jahirul et al., 2012). Hemicellulose decomposes approximately at temperature range 250 – 400°C, cellulose at temperature range 300-420°C. Carbon fixed into these 2 compounds is regarded as volatile matter. Lignin decomposes only partly, for this reason part of the carbon stored in lignin is regarded as fixed carbon. High lignin content contributes to higher biochar yield, while biomass high cellulose content has higher bio-oil yield (Jahirul et al., 2012).

Table 4. Cellulose, hemi-cellulose and lignin content in different feedstocks.

<i>Feedstock</i>	<i>Cellulose [%]</i>	<i>Hemi-cellulose [%]</i>	<i>Lignin [%]</i>
Brewers spent grains	3.61 - 18.54	26.50 – 52.75	12.97 – 39.37
Sugarcane leaf	38.7 – 53.8	24 – 34.4	13.2 – 18.9
Sugarcane bagasse	19 – 24	42 – 48	23 – 32
Cotton seed hulls	80 – 95	5 – 20	0
Cotton stalks	38 – 57	12 – 18	8 – 20
Rice husk	34	28	18
Rice straw	32.11	24	18
Grape pomace	24.95	27.38	21.37
Tomato pomace	32.09	26.62	30.54
Tomato stems	30 – 40	4 – 12	4 – 14

Summary of proximate analysis and determination of the level of cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin basing on analysed literature (Borel et al., 2020; Castro et al., 2025; Da Silva Araújo et al., 2025; Gupta et al., 2016; He et al., 2019; Huang et al., 2010; Jahirul et al., 2012; Llorach-Massana et al. 2017; Manríquez-Altamirano et al., 2021; Palliprath et al., 2020; Pirozzi et al., 2022) was presented in table 4. In general, the analysed biomasses can be divided into those with a high content of fixed carbon and lignin, which include brewers' spent grains, grape pomace, tomato pomace, and sugarcane bagasse. Pyrolysis of such types of biomass is characterized by a higher biochar yield. Biomasses with a high content of cellulose and hemicellulose, and thus a higher volatile matter content (e.g. cotton seeds), produce a lower biochar yield but a higher bio-oil yield.

Properties of biochar

Agronomic potential of biochar use depends on its physical and chemical properties, which are highly diverse, and influenced by several factors, including the diameter of biochar particles and the rate of temperature increase during pyrolysis. The most influential factors are, however, the maximal temperature of the pyrolysis and the feedstock used (Lehmann & Joseph, 2024). To systematize the knowledge of properties of biochars derived from the feedstocks of interest, the summary of the properties of biochars derived from tomato residues, rice husk and straw, sugarcane leave and bagasse, cotton stalk, cotton seed hulk, grape pomace, and brewer spent grains was summarized and presented in the supplemental material (S1).

Biochar yield decreases with increasing temperature of pyrolysis. This pattern occurs in the case of the pyrolysis of tomato pomace (from 8.1 to 4.5% in temperature range 350-450°C ; Stylianou et al. 2023), cottonseed hull (from 83.4 to 24.3% in temperature range 200-800°C;

Tao et al. 2024, Uchimiya et al. 2011), cotton stalk (from 71.2 to 31.4% in temperature range 250-650°C; Tao et al. 2024; Gao et al., 2021), and brewers spent grains (from 25.1 to 19.9% in temperature range 250-650°C; Borel et al., 2020). This decrease in yield with increasing temperature fits into the trend described by Jahirul et al. (2012). According to their technological review, which also considers yields of bio-oils and syngas, as the temperature increases, the biochar yield decreases, the yield of syngas increases, and the yield of bio-oil increase up to around 500°C, after which it begin to decrease again (Figure 1). The influence of the heating rate on biochar’s yield is also visible in the data set. Phuong et al. (2015) observed higher biochar yield in lower heating rates in case of rice straw and rice husk biomass. Borel et al. (2020) observed the highest biochar yield in the lowest heating rates within the same maximum pyrolysis temperatures after brewers spent grains pyrolysis. As mentioned in paragraph “Feedstock categorization for biochar production”, biochar yield is significantly affected by the fixed carbon content and ash content of the original biomass.

Figure 1. The percentage yield of the final products of the pyrolysis of biomass. Source: Uddin et al (2018)

The carbon content of biochar strongly depends on the maximum temperature of pyrolysis. With increasing temperature of pyrolysis, the carbon content of the biochar also increases (Phuong et al, 2015; Asadi et al., 2021; Jeong et al., 2015; Tao et al. 2024; Manolikaki and Diamadopoulos, 2015; Borel et al., 2020), as the biomass undergo aromatization process, in which part of the carbon stay in the solid fraction, while other elements such as oxygen, hydrogen or nitrogen volatilize (Brown et al., 2024). Consequently, the content of oxygen

and hydrogen decreases with the increasing maximum temperature of pyrolysis. The aromatized form of carbon is less prone for decomposition (Petersen & Sanei, 2025), therefore the H/C and O/C ratios are widely utilized as a proxy for carbon stability. International Biochar Initiative guidelines (IBI, 2015) set the benchmark of “stable” biochar on 0.7 H/C, and European Biochar Certificate (EBC, 2025) considers biochar with an H/C ratio below 0.4 as “highly stable,” with substantial fractions of aromatic carbon expected to persist in soil for millennia. In the analysed data, pyrolysis of certain feedstocks (sugar cane bagasse and leave/trash, cotton stalks, rice straw) resulted in lower H/C at relatively low temperatures, suggesting they achieved higher levels of aromatization earlier than others (brewers spent grains, cottonseed hull, rice husk). In general, temperature of pyrolysis over 700°C allows to classify all the kinds of biochars as “highly stable” according to EBC (202) and temperature over 400°C as “stable” according to IBI (2015) (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Pyrolysis temperature vs. H/C ratio.

Nutrient content is dependent mostly on the feedstock type. Nitrogen levels are generally much higher in the biochars produced out of brewers spent grains (av. 4.89%; Borel et al. 2020), followed by green tomato residues (1.6%; Dunlop et al. 2015), grapes pomace (1.5%; Manolikaki and Diamadopoulos, 2015) and cotton byproducts (av. 1.44%; Tao et al. 2024; Uchimiya et al. 2011; Gao et al., 2021). Biochars produced out of sugar cane bagasse (av. 0.44%; Jeong et al., 2015), rice husk (av. 0.69%; Asadi et al., 2021; Phuong et al, 2015; Jeong

et al., 2015; Manolikaki and Diamadopoulos, 2015), and sugarcane leaves (av. 0.83%; Jeong et al., 2015) are characterized by the lowest levels of N. Within most of subgroups of different feedstock origin (sugarcane leaves and bagasse, rice straw, cotton stalks, brewers spent grains) there is visible pattern of decrease of N content with increasing temperature of pyrolysis, what aligns with results of Liu et al. (2019). For rice husk and cottonseed hulk, this pattern is however not visible.

Data on phosphorus (P) and potassium (K) content are more limited within the data set. P content is the highest in green tomato residues biochar (1.39%; Dunlop et al, 2015), and tomato pomace biochar (av. 1.32%; Stylianou et al, 2023). Those values are quite high, giving some potential in P recycling, however still twice to six times lower compared to biochars regarded as P-rich such as poultry litter biochar, biogas fibre biochar or pig manure biochar (Robinson et al., 2018; Laghari et al., 2021). The values of P content of biochars derived from sugarcane waste (av. 0.19%; Jeong et al., 2015), rice straw (av. 0.25%; Jeong et al., 2015), and grape pomace (0.36%; Manolikaki and Diamadopoulos, 2015) are very low, in practice meaning a negligible effect on enriching the soil with phosphorus. Notably, the levels of P increase with the increase of the pyrolysis temperature in cases of all kinds of original feedstock. As already mentioned, the bioavailability of P in biochar is lower than in the original biomass (Laghari et al., 2021), which effect was not investigated by the analysed studies. For K, biochars produced out of pomace of tomato (av. 22.18%; Stylianou et al. 2023) and grapes (7.1%; Manolikaki and Diamadopoulos, 2015) show particularly high values compared to the other kinds of biochar. Average values of K content were measured in rice straw biochar (av. 3.26%; Jeong et al., 2015), and sugar cane leave biochar (av. 2.17%; Jeong et al., 2015), while K content in rice husk biochar (av. 0.88%; Asadi et al., 2021; Jeong et al., 2015) and sugarcane bagasse (av. 0.81%; Jeong et al., 2015) was the lowest. Similarly as in the case of P, K content in biochar increases with the increase of temperature of pyrolysis, even after exceeding the threshold of 600°C, when K starts to volatilize according to Liu et al. (2019). Availability of K from the biochar was also not studied in the analysed literature. In general around 50% of K in biochar is estimated bio-available, with the peak of availability at temperature of pyrolysis of 400°C (Liu et al., 2019).

Nearly all biochars studied have alkaline pH (Figure 3), a part of biochars derived from brewers spent grains (av. pH =6.88; Da Silva Araújo et al., 2025). Across feedstocks there is an observable trend of increasing pH with increasing temperature of pyrolysis. Average pH values vary by feedstock.. In general, biochars produced out of rice husk (av. pH=8.72; Asadi

et al., 2021; Phuong et al, 2015; Jeong et al., 2015; Manolikaki and Diamadopoulos, 2015), have lower pH than biochars produced out of rice straw (av. pH=10.41; Phuong et al, 2015; Jeong et al., 2015), and biochars produced out of sugar bagasse (av. pH=8.29; Jeong et al., 2015) have lower pH than biochars produced out of sugar leaves (av. pH=8.92; Jeong et al., 2015). Biochars produced out of green tomato residues (pH=10.40; Dunlop et al. 2015), tomato pomace (av. pH=10.70; Stylianou et al. 2023) and grape pomace (pH= 10.22; Manolikaki and Diamadopoulos, 2015) are among the most alkaline. The large variability of pH in different biochars makes it possible to individually adjust the type of biochar. For most soils in Maharashtra, which are alkaline (Hadole et. al 2020), slightly alkaline biochars (brewers spent grains, rice husk, sugarcane bagasse produced at low pyrolysis temperature) would be more suitable, while in acidic lateritic soils, the use of more alkaline biochars may bring more positive effects.

Figure 3. Pyrolysis temperature vs. pH

Specific Surface Area (SSA) is an important property of the biochar, that is representing its adsorptive properties, which plays a key role in the remediation of soils contaminated with heavy metals (Singh et al., 2024). SSA has a tendency to grow with increasing pyrolysis

temperature. This pattern occurs in the case of the pyrolysis of tomato pomace (Stylianou et al. 2023), rice husk (Phuong et al, 2015; Asadi et al., 2021), rice straw (Phuong et al, 2015; Jeong et al., 2015), and cottonseed hull (Tao et al. 2024; Uchimiya et al. 2011). Higher values of SSA occur after pyrolysis of a biomass of a low ash content (eg. rice straw, rice husk, cottonseed hull, sugarcane leaves) in comparison to biomass of a high ash content (eg. tomato pomace). High lignin content of the original feedstock also favours high SSA (Bai et al., 2024).

Cation Exchange Capacity (CEC) is a property that depicts capacity to adsorb nutrients (Bai et al., 2024). Generally, the higher the CEC, the greater the soil's ability to store nutrients. Biochar as a soil amendment has the ability to increase CEC of the soil, as its own CEC can be as much as 100 times higher than the CEC of agricultural soil (Beesley et al., 2024). Within the database, CEC values are closely related to the type of biomass used for pyrolysis (Figure 4). The lowest CEC values are found in biochars produced from rice husk (3.1-62.6 cmol/kg; Phuong et al, 2015; Asadi et al., 2021; Jeong et al., 2015). Medium values are observed in biochars produced from green tomato residues (49.7 cmol/kg ; Dunlop et al. 2015), rice straw (45.6-68.6 cmol/kg; Phuong et al, 2015; Jeong et al., 2015), and sugar cane bagasse (50.0-92.8 cmol/kg; Jeong et al., 2015). The highest CEC values are found in biochars produced from sugar cane leaves (83.0-113.7; Jeong et al., 2015). The values of CEC decrease with increase of temperature of pyrolysis, which is related to the progressing process of aromatization, therefore reducing the abundance of oxygenated functional groups, which are responsible for CEC of biochar (Beesley et al., 2024).

Figure 4. Pyrolysis temperature vs. CEC

As explained in the following section “Potential agricultural benefits of a biochar use in Maharashtra”, properties of biochar should be appropriately selected to the needs of the soil. Trends in biochar properties were summarized in the table below (Table 5).

Table 5. Summary of properties of different biochars

Biochar kind		Carbon stability	Nutrient content	pH	Specific Surface Area	Cation Exchange Capacity
Feedstock	Temperature					
Brewers spent grains	Low (<400°C)	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d
	Medium (400-600°C)	Medium	High in N	Slightly acidic	n.d.	n.d.
	High (>600°C)	High	High in N	Slightly alkaline	n.d.	n.d.
Sugarcane leaf	Low	n.d	Low	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
	Medium	High	Low	Slightly alkaline	Medium to high	High
	High	High	High in K	Strongly alkaline	Very high	High
Sugarcane bagasse	Low	n.d.	Low	n.d.	n.d	n.d.
	Medium	High	Low	Slightly alkaline	High	Medium to high
	High	High	Low	Slightly alkaline	n.d.	Medium
Cotton stalk	Low	High	Low in N	n.d.	Medium	n.d.
	Medium	High	Low in N	n.d.	Medium	n.d.
	High	High	Low in N	n.d.	Medium	n.d.
Cotton seed hull	Low	Low	Low in N	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
	Medium	Medium to high	Low in N	n.d.	Medium	n.d.
	High	High	Low in N	n.d.	Medium to very high	n.d.
Rice husk	Low	Low	Low	Slightly alkaline	Medium	Low to medium
	Medium	Medium to high	Low to high in P	Slightly acidic to strongly alkaline	Medium to very high	Low to medium
	High	High	Low	Slightly alkaline to strongly alkaline	Medium to high	Low
Rice straw	Low	High	n.d	n.d.	Medium	n.d.
	Medium	High	High in K	Slightly alkaline to strongly alkaline	Medium to high	Medium
	High	High	High in K	Strongly alkaline	Very high	Medium
Grape pomace	Low	n.d	n.d	Strongly alkaline	n.d.	n.d.
	Medium	n.d	Low in P	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
	High	n.d	n.d	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
Tomato pomace	Low	n.d	n.d	Strongly alkaline	Medium	n.d.
	Medium	n.d	High in P	Strongly alkaline	Medium	n.d.
Tomato stems	Medium	Medium	High in P	Strongly alkaline	n.d.	Medium

Potential agricultural benefits of a biochar use in Maharashtra

Potential agricultural benefits of biochar use depends both on the properties of the soil and the properties of the biochar. Maharashtra exhibits a complex diversity of soils.. The most wide-spread, especially in agriculture-intensive regions are: black cotton soils (vertisols), and red soils (alfisols and inceptisols). Black soils are mostly rich in clay minerals, therefore have high water holding capacity, and poor drainage. They are alkaline in pH, poor in organic carbon and low in N, S, and P. Red soils have low CEC, low organic matter content, and acidic pH. Lateritic and coastal saline soils are common in the coastal region. Lateritic soils are rich in sesquioxides, have high clay content, low organic matter content, they are poor in nutrients, toxic in aluminium and manganese, and hard in texture. Saline soils are characterized by very high EC and pH between slightly acidic and slightly alkaline (Das, 2015).

Figure 5. Agroecological regions of Maharashtra. Source: National Bureau of Soil Survey and Land Use (1996), Maharashtra Soils.

Research carried out in Solapur region (south-central Maharashtra) by Hadole (2020), has shown that the average pH in the superficial soil layer is neutral to alkaline. The organic carbon content varied significantly, as did calcium carbonate content (Table 6). Borkar et. al (2018) present data from the coastal region with division for different soil kinds. The data for black soils are similar to those for the central region of the state. Lateritic soils, on the other hand, are characterized by lower pH and higher organic carbon content. The authors also examined the levels of major macronutrients. Their findings indicate that nitrogen and potassium contents are similar in both soil types, whereas the phosphorus content is noticeably lower in lateritic soils.

Table 6. Chemical properties of superficial soil layer in Maharashtra. Sources: Borkar et. al (2018), Hadole et. al (2020)

pH (1:2.5)	EC(dS/m)	CaCO ₃ (%)	Organic Carbon (g/kg)	CEC (cmol/kg)	Av. Nitrogen (kg/ha)	Av. P ₂ O ₅ (kg/ha)	Av. K ₂ O (kg/ha)
Solapur region (central Maharashtra), without differentiation for kinds of soils; Hadole et. al (2020)							
7.95	0.14	7.87	7.33	[-]	[-]	[-]	[-]
Konkan region (coastal area); Borkar et. al (2018)							
Lateritic soil							
5.80	0.08	[-]	18	28.40	298.8	9.1	229.8
Coastal saline soil							
7.30	3.8	[-]	7.8	46.6	312.4	23.4	972.8
Black soil							
7.00	0.14	[-]	12.9	40.86	258.3	18.4	270

There is a research gap regarding application of biochar to black cotton soils (vertisols) in India. It is documented that biochar can improve some properties of black soil such as CEC, nutrient content, water drainage or organic carbon content. Alkaline properties of biochar can however cause an increase of soil pH, which in case of already alkaline soils can lead to reduced nutrient availability, particularly Ca, Fe, B, Mn (Reitsma et al., 2011). Karthik et al. (2019) in his experiment carried out on alkaline soils (pH=8.15) in Tamil Nadu documented increased soil porosity, CEC, and organic carbon content after application of biochars derived from maize, cotton and prosopis. pH of the soil increased after application of high pH biochar (prosobis biochar; pH=8.70), but did not grow drastically after application of lower pH biochars (cotton biochar, maize biochar). Soni et al. (2023) also did not document a vast increase in soil pH after application of chick pea straw biochar (pH=8.19) to black cotton soil. Akanji et al., 2022 however documents substantial increase in soil pH after conocarpus biochar (pH=9.83) application to alkaline sandy soil (pH=8.20). In their study, despite the

increased soil pH, the application of biochar to the soil improved other soil health parameters, which in turn resulted in higher yield and enhanced growth of fodder crops. In light of the above information, the application of biochar with a relatively low pH appears to improve yields on black alkaline soils. The negative effect of further increases in soil pH is expected to be minor, so the beneficial impacts of biochar should prevail. Nevertheless, caution is advised when applying biochar to alkaline soils, particularly under long-term use. The influence of biochar on this specific soil type in India also seems to require more detailed investigation.

Mahato et al. (2020) identified agrarian problem of lateritic soils in India, highlighting low plant available water capacity, nutrient deficiencies, high soil acidity, which reduces nutrient availability, toxicities of aluminium (Al) and manganese (Mg), which under acidic conditions are harmful to plant roots, low CEC due to dominance of 1:1 clays (kaolinite) and poor organic matter content. Rajakumar (2019) in his PhD thesis argues that biochar of coconut shell application helped to improve almost all the regarded aspects of soil health, which lead to increased yield of potato and cowpea. Mahato et al., (2020) documented increase in eggplant yield by 77% after amending the soil with 10t/ha of biochar produced in low cost, portable clin. In case of lateritic soils, liming is particularly important in enhancing soil health, therefore biochars of high pH should be applied in those kinds of soils. The biochar should also have possibly high CEC and nutritional content.

Improvement of saline soil properties was reported in several studies. In saline soils several problems such as reduced microbial activity, low CEC and reduced nutrient-holding capacity occur due to its low organic matter content (Liang et al., 2005). Singh et al. (2019) in their soil incubation experiment carried out in Punjab, found out that despite the fact, that rice waste biochar application led to further increase in their EC, the negative effects of the salinity such as reduce in cumulative respiration and microbial biomass carbon were reduced to the levels similar as to not-saline soils at biochar application rate of 2-4% for a soil of EC=8.30. They state that the high surface area of the biochar as well as its capacity to provide labile carbon compounds, enhancing microbial activity, are responsible for this phenomenon. Huang et al. (2019) documented an increase in maize yield by 34 % as a result of woodchip biochar application at 5% rate in coastal saline soil (EC=4.15) in China. Cui et al. (2022) found that application of biochar improved saline-alkali soil properties and microstructure, increasing soil water holding capacity, total organic carbon content, and cation exchange capacity, and reducing total salt content which led to increased yield of maize and wheat. Abulaiti et al., 2022 in a 5 year season period also documented decrease in total salt content

and improvement of soil health as well as increase in rice yield. They suggest that decrease in salt content might have been caused by improvement of the soil water content and adsorption of Na ions by biochar. This mechanism would suggest that biochars of high SSA, therefore produced out of lignin-rich feedstock at high temperatures (Bai et al., 2024) should provide better results in coastal saline soils improvement.

Environmental risks

Despite providing numerous well-documented benefits, biochar may provoke risks for soil health in several different mechanisms. Xiang et al. (2021) summarized existing knowledge about environmental hazards related to biochar use, highlighting presence of harmful components such as:

1. Heavy metals, which content in biochar mainly depend on heavy metal content in original biomass, and mainly refers to feedstocks such as sewage sludge or specific kinds of wood. With increasing temperature of pyrolysis, the content of heavy metals increases, as they mostly accumulate in stable products. Biochars of a higher SSA have higher heavy metal concentration in the exchangeable fraction, which may lead to higher heavy metal bioavailability (von Gunten et al., 2017). World Biochar Certificate (WBC, 2023), recognized by the biggest carbon offset generators (Puro.earth, Verra), provides maximal values allowed of Pb, Cd, Cu, Ni, Hg, Zn, Cr, and As in biochar.
2. Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), that have mutagenic properties. In contrast to heavy metals, PAHs do not occur in original feedstocks, but are products of pyrolysis process itself. Pyrolysis conditions have a crucial impact on the content of PAHs. Hale et al. (2012) documented that PAH concentration in biochar decreases with increasing maximal temperature of pyrolysis. Slow pyrolysis biochar also has lower content of PAHs than fast pyrolysis biochar. The same study reports that bioavailability of PAHs is the highest in biochars produced at low temperatures. World Biochar Certificate (2024) requires that the summarized content of main 16 PAHs in premium biochar do not exceed 6 g/t of dry mass of biochar. For comparison De la Rosa et al., (2019) did document the decrease of main 16 PAHs content from 6.36 g/t to 1.29 g/t with increase of rice husk pyrolysis temperature from 400°C to 600°C.

3. Dioxins - organic compounds containing chlorine, which are stable in the environment, and toxic for animal and human health. Food waste, that frequently has a high salt content, has been shown to produce biochar of significant amounts of dioxins. European Biochar Certificate (2024) expresses toxicity of dioxins by toxicity equivalency quotient (TEQ), and that value should not exceed 20 ng/kg TEQ. TEQ was documented to be much lower even in food waste biochar (1.2 ng/kg; Hale et al., 2012), what indicate that in general the dioxin content in biochar is low (Xiang et al., 2021)
4. Environmentally persistent free radicals (EPFRs), which are long-lived, free radicals that can persist in the environment and may pose environmental risk, as they induce formation of reactive oxygen species, that have high phytotoxicity and cytotoxicity. Precursors of EPFRs in biomass are mostly cellulose, hemi-cellulose and lignin. Increase in pyrolysis temperature up to around 500°C resulted in increased concentration of EPFRs in biochar. As the total concentration of EPFRs cannot directly represent toxicity index, the bioavailability of EPFRs should be used (Xiang et al., 2021). For now, international certification standards such as European Biochar Certificate and World Biochar Certificate do not contain guidelines regarding EPFRs content (EBC, 2024; WBC, 2023). The state of knowledge about their presence in biochar is limited compared to other toxic substances such as heavy metals or PAHs (Xiang et al., 2021). In order to reduce biochar EPFRs content Chen et al. (2025), suggest controlling pyrolysis temperature (<400°C or over >700°C), and decreasing the lignocellulose content of the feedstock through a predigestion step. The same authors conclude, that although the environmental harm of free radicals is well established, no widespread harmful effects of biochar produced at 400–700 °C have been reported in agro-ecosystems or animals, what suggests that the scale of risk provoke EPFRs in biochar is not alarming.
5. Volatile Organic Compounds (VOC) – biotoxic substances including acetone, benzene, methyl ethyl ketone, and toluene. They are mostly present in pyrolysis gas, and partly can stay in biochar surfaces and pores. VOC, similarly to PAHs, are reduced in content with increasing temperature of pyrolysis, therefore high pyrolysis temperature allows for production of safer biochar in terms of VOC content. The World Biochar Certificate determines VOC by thermogravimetric analysis in the first control of the pyrolysis unit (WBC, 2023).

Although positive effects of biochar on crop growth are well documented, there are examples of research which did not result in obtaining higher crop yields after biochar application. Within 45 studies analysed by Spokas et al. (2011) approximately 50% of them proved that biochar had positive effects on crop growth or yield, 30% of selected reports had no significant effect, and 20% even documented inhibited crop growth or yield. Xiang et al. (2021) refer some examples of failures in yield results to increased concentration of toxic substances such as heavy metals, VOC, EPFRs or PAHs, but additionally highlight phenomenon of nutrient absorption by biochar, what leads to their lower bioavailability. Due to its high SSA, biochar was documented also to absorb plant hormones, signal compounds of mycorrhizal fungi, as well as pesticides, which could lead to the excessive use of pesticides in agricultural production and cause pesticide accumulation in the environment (Xiang et al., 2021).

Biochar can also play a role in migration of non-biochar derived pollutions, as due to its high absorption properties, it can carry various substances such as heavy metals. Nano-particles of biochar, which are created during biochar weathering, are specially prone to transportation via surface runoff and infiltration into groundwaters (Xiang et al., 2021). What is more, biochar production can lead to air pollution, as the pyrolysis results in toxic PM production, that is specially what is particularly significant in small-scale low-tech pyrolysis systems (Xiang et al., 2021).

In summary, some mechanisms of environmental risks are well-studied and included in well-established certification systems, therefore possible to avoid using proper feedstocks and pyrolysis conditions (high pyrolysis temperature prevents formation of biochar rich in PAHs and VOC, low heavy metal content in original feedstock prevent from high heavy metal content in biochar). Some others such as EPFRs require further research and guidance. Overall however in most research analysed the effects of biochar application on agricultural land turned out to be positive.

Technoeconomic analysis and LCA

Technoeconomic analysis of the industrial process requires calculation of the material balance and energy balance, as well as selling prizes and operating expenses, in order to calculate the operating expenditure (OPEX) and capital expenditure (CAPEX), which serve to calculate Present Value (PV) and Net Present Value (NPV) (Vishwanath, 2020). OPEX is the expense

occurring in regular day-to-day activity of the business such as salary for workers, rent, taxes etc. CAPEX are funds used by the company to buy, upgrade or maintain long-term assets. PV and NPV are financial metrics that discount future cash flows to their current value, accounting for the time value of money, and are used to assess project feasibility. A positive NPV indicates viability, while a negative NPV indicates non-viability. Technoeconomic analyses usually also contain sensitivity analysis, which analyzes the effect of change of market variables such as selling prices and costs on NPV (Vishwanath, 2020).

Material balance and energy balance are process-specific and require detailed information regarding the projected pyrolysis process. Material balance, however, is easier to identify from the existing literature, as many scientific reports about biochar mention its yield, with some of them also including yield of bio-oil and syngas (see section Properties of biochar).

The selection of appropriate pyrolysis conditions is therefore important for the profitability of pyrolysis, as different pyrolysis products have different market prices. An additional gain of the process is generation of carbon credits, which can be sold on a voluntary market (Joseph et al., 2024). As the climate regulations in many countries become more strict, the prize of the carbon credits is expected to grow (BloombergNEF). Sample prizes of pyrolysis products and carbon credits are presented in the table below (Tab. 7).

Table 7. Sample prices of pyrolysis products and carbon credits

Product	Selling price (US\$)	Source
Biochar (per kg)	0.75	Average from the offers found on
Bio-oil (per l)	0.81	indiamart.com (retrieved 6 th of
Bio-methanol (per l)	0.33	August, 2025)
Carbon credit (per t of CO ₂)	110-160	European Biochar Market Report, 2025

Revenue can be calculated by multiplying projected generation of products from specific kinds of pyrolysis by selling prices. An important component of (OPEX) is the cost of collection, transportation, and storage of the biomass, frequently considered cost-prohibitive (Sahoo et al., 2020). Currently, many feasible biochar production projects are based on large industrial plants located at points in the supply chain where a large amount of biomass is available. These include biogas plants, wastewater treatment plants, or processing sites of

agricultural products (European Biochar, 2025). Large scale plants offer the possibility of precise control over pyrolysis conditions in order to obtain specific biochar parameters and produce bio-fuels. On the other hand, in many currently operating schemes the owner of technology retains the profit from the sale of carbon credits (Stiesdal SkyClean; MASH Makes), which limits the share of profits for farmers on whose land the biochar is deposited. Alternative solutions include small-scale portable pyrolysis plants, that can be easily transported to biomass location, which substantially reduces transportation costs (Sahoo et al.; 2020, Takechar) or in the simplest form kon-tiki klins - conical boilers in which biomass is burned and simple pits. The accumulation of CO₂, which is heavier than oxygen, in the lower part of the boiler, or the pit creates conditions with lack of oxygen in which part of the biomass undergoes pyrolysis (The biochar revolution; Brown et al., 2024). Less advanced and at the same time cheaper technologies could be more accessible to local communities, which could potentially be included in the economic benefits (Joseph et al., 2024). Their drawback is, however, limited control over the pyrolysis process, therefore limited capacity or total lack of capacity of production of bio-fuels and less predictable properties of biochar, which can potentially result in higher environmental risk. Further progress of technoeconomic analysis requires data specific to the chosen technological solution.

Figure 6. Biochar production technologies. On the left is the kon-tiki klin. On the right is an industrial pyrolysis plant allowing for extraction of bio-fuels.

Life cycle assessment (LCA) is a standardized method that helps to analyse the environmental impact of the product in its entire life cycle – since extraction of resources, through production, transport, utilization to recycling. LCA consists of target definition and scope, life cycle inventory analysis, life cycle impact assessment, and interpretation (Xiang et al., 2021). LCA can take into consideration various effects of a biochar system operating such as net green house emissions, possible gain from increased crop production, negative impact on environment from pollutants within biochar or air pollution from biochar production in less advanced pyrolysis units. LCA was used in several published research to assess environmental biochar system efficiency. For example, Sahoo et al. (2020) proved that small scale portable biochars systems are environmentally beneficial in the context of American forest management. Azzi et al. (2019) compared different systems of district heating in

Stockholm, indicating that pyrolysis units might be providing carbon dioxide removal, along with district heat and benefits for agriculture. Owsianiak et al. (2018) in the research carried out in six developing and middle income countries (Ethiopia, Indonesia, Kenya, Peru, Vietnam, and China) showed that pyrolysis systems provided in specific conditions more environmental benefits than composting. Llorach-Massana et al. (2017) analysed small-scale and industrial biochar system's carbon capture efficiency in Spain, and highlighted the importance of appropriate moisture of a feedstock and small distance of feedstock transport in order to obtain a carbon negative system. LCA might be a very useful tool for future work within consortium e.g. to compare different biochar systems in India or to compare systems that include pyrolysis with other biomass utilization ideas.

4. Conclusion and Future Directions

This study shows the potential of pyrolysis as a way of biomass residues management. Current residue management is inefficient, with on-farm burning, being wide-spread and leading to severe air pollution and greenhouse emissions. Assuming that carbon constitutes about 40% of sugarcane biomass (Kumar et al., 2022), and 40% of this carbon could be stabilized in the form of biochar (Rodrigues et al., 2023), of which 60% would remain stable (IBI, 2015), if only half of the sugarcane residues in Maharashtra was pyrolyzed, annual CO₂ emissions would be reduced by around 5,5 Mt of CO₂ equivalent, what is comparable to 6 days of all greenhouse gases emission of entire state of Maharashtra (iFOREST, 2024). This applies to other kinds of biomass residues as well. The key issue, however, seems to be existing barriers that prevent farmers from collecting agricultural residues from the fields, with huge land fragmentation that limits the possibility of mechanization. Understanding this and other barriers would make it possible to estimate to what extent the proposed solution, pyrolysis, could change the current management of residues.

Biochar properties, which have significant implication for soil improvement are strongly influenced by original feedstock type and pyrolysis condition. Agrarian benefits include enhanced CEC, water retention, soil liming, and nutrient recycling, which lead to increased yield and plant growth parameters documented in numerous researches. The analysis of soil types in Maharashtra indicated that biochar would be specially beneficial for nutrient-poor, acidic lateritic and red soils, as well as saline coastal soils. For black cotton soils, the choice

of biochar with moderate pH is important to avoid further alkalization, however further research in this topic seems to be needed.

Most environmental risks of biochar are well documented, and can be avoided by appropriate feedstock selection and optimized pyrolysis conditions. Certification systems such as the World Biochar Certificate, already set safety standards for heavy metals, PAHs, dioxins and VOC. The topic of EPFRs is however quite new and requires further research.

While techno-economic and life cycle assessments were not within the full scope of this study, preliminary insights suggest that the economic feasibility depends strongly on biomass availability, transportation costs, and technological choice. Large-scale pyrolysis plants provide more predictable properties of biochar, while smaller portable pyrolysis units may provide local accessibility and farmer participation, though with less control over biochar quality. Further, more detailed comparable analysis between large scale pyrolysis plants and low scale, portable solutions would provide more insights in advantages and disadvantages of both solutions in specific sites. It is also important to compare pyrolysis as a residue management practice with other ideas such as usage of the residues in chemical, food or pharmaceutical industry, as potential revenues might be higher, which could solve the issue of particular biomass residues much more efficiently. For these applications LCA seems to be an appropriate methodology.

This report does not consider issues related to existing strategies and programmes in India, which could help implement the discussed technology in practice. This seems to be an important area of focus in the coming years.

In conclusion, biochar production from Maharashtra's abundant agricultural residues offers a promising pathway for carbon sequestration with potential of waste valorisation by producing valuable soil amendment and revenue from the carbon offset market. However, successful implementation will require site-specific matching of biochar to soil types, careful management of risks, and further work on techno-economic feasibility to support decision-making.

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